

5th International Conference on Environmental Radioactivity

Variations of Environmental Radionuclides

**8 – 13 September 2019
Prague Czech Republic**

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Local Organizing Committee

I. Světlík (Chair), Nuclear Physics Institute of the CAS, Prague
M. Němec, (Vice-Chair) Czech Technical University in Prague
M. Molnár, ATOMKI, Debrecen
T. Němcová, Czech Technical University in Prague
K. Pachnerová Brabcová, Nuclear Physics Institute of the CAS, Prague
Z. A. Ovšonková, Nuclear Physics Institute of the CAS, Prague
M. Petrová, Nuclear Physics Institute of the CAS, Prague
N. Megisová, Nuclear Physics Institute of the CAS, Prague
V. Suchý, Nuclear Physics Institute of the CAS, Prague
R. Garba, Nuclear Physics Institute of the CAS, Prague
J. Šneberger, Nuclear Physics Institute of the CAS, Prague

International Organizing Committee

P.P. Povinec (Chair), Comenius University, Bratislava
I. Světlík (Co-Chair), Nuclear Physics Institute of the CAS
F. Bréchnignac, International Union of Radioecology, Paris
M. Garcia León, University of Sevilla
A. Ioannidou, Aristotle University, Thessaloniki
G. Lujanienė, Center for Physical Sciences and Technology, Vilnius
S.C. Sheppard, Chief Editor, Journal of Environmental Radioactivity

International Advisory Board

P.P. Povinec (Chair), Comenius University, Bratislava
I. Světlík (Co-Chair), Nuclear Physics Institute of the CAS
L. Benedik, Josef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana
E. Boaretto, Weizmann Institute of Science, Rehovot
A.E. Cherkinsky, University of Georgia, Athens
R. Garcia-Tenorio, University of Sevilla
M. Hult, EC, Joint Research Centre - Institute for Reference Materials and Measurements, Geel
S. Jerome, IAEA-EL, Monaco
J. John, Czech Technical University in Prague
A.J.T. Jull, University of Arizona, Tucson
W.E. Kieser, University of Ottawa
T. Kovacs, Pannonia University
J. Kučera, Nuclear Physics Institute of the CAS
O. Masson, Institut de Sureté Nucléaire, Saint-Paul-lez-Durance
M. Molnár, ATOMKI, Debrecen
S. Pan, University of Nanjing
A. Rakowski, SUT, Gliwice
P. Steier, University of Vienna
G. Steinhauser, University of Hannover
E. Steinnes, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim
F. Terrasi, CIRCE, Caserta
C. Tsabaris, Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, Anavyssos
P. Vojtyla, CERN, Geneva
G. Wallner, University of Vienna
G. Wallova, WRI, Bratislava

Invited speakers

M. Aoyama, Tsukuba University
F. Bréchnignac, Institut de Sureté Nucléaire, Saint-Paul-lez-Durance
A. Chatt, Dalhousie University, Halifax
M. Clemenza, University of Milano - Bicocca
K. Hirose, Sophia University, Tokyo
X. Hou, Technical University of Denmark, Riso
A.J.T. Jull, University of Arizona, Tucson
Y. Kumamoto, JAMSTEC, Yokosuka
J. Kučera, Nuclear Physics Institute of the CAS, Prague
M. Laubenstein, GSNL, Assergi
G. Lujanienė, SRI Center for Physical Sciences and Technology, Vilnius
S.-H. Lee, Korea Research Institute of Standards and Sciences, Daejeon
I. Levin, University of Heidelberg
O. Masson, Institut de Sureté Nucléaire, Saint-Paul-lez-Durance
J-W. Mietelski, PAS, Krakow
M. Molnár, ATOMKI, Debrecen
T. Nakanishi, University of Tokyo
S. Nisi, GSNL, Assergi
B. Salbu, Norwegian University of Life Sciences
P. Steier, University of Vienna
G. Steinhauser, University of Hannover
H-A. Synal, ETH, Zurich
V. Wagner, Nuclear Physics Institute of the CAS, Prague
N. Yasuda, Fukui University, Fukui

Radionuclides in drinking water in Vojvodina and health implication

N. Todorović¹, J. Nikolov¹, I. Stojković², B. Tenjović¹, A. Vraničar¹, J. Hansman¹, S. Lučić³, S. Bjelović⁴

¹Department of Physics, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, 21000, Serbia

²Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, 21000, Serbia

³Institute of Oncology of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, 21208, Serbia

⁴Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, 21000, Serbia

Keywords: drinking water, gross alpha, LSC, gamma-spectrometry, total dose

Presenting author, e-mail: natasa.todorovic@df.uns.ac.rs

Drinking water may contain radioactive isotopes that pose potential risks to human health. Isotopes from uranium-238 series dominantly contribute to the irradiation risks due to the ingestion of a drinking water. Because of its potential public health hazard, the surveys of radioactivity in water sources are necessary.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), when activity concentration in drinking water exceeds the recommended level of 0.1 BqL^{-1} for gross- α or 1 BqL^{-1} for gross- β activities, radionuclide-specific concentrations should be brought into compliance with WHO guidance levels (WHO, 2011).

Gross alpha/beta activity concentrations in investigated water samples were determined by liquid scintillation counter, Quantulus 1220. Ultra-low level liquid scintillation counting coupled to alpha/beta discrimination allows rapid and simple determination of gross alpha and beta activities that are simultaneously measured through alpha/beta discrimination technique.

The radionuclide content of the drinking water samples was determined from a cumulative sample by gamma-spectrometry measurements using the HPGe spectrometer. The nominal efficiency of the detector is 36% and the resolution is 1.9 keV. The detector was operated inside the 12-cm-thick lead shield with a 3-mm Cu inner layer. The sample measurement time was 50 ks. The gamma spectra were acquired and analyzed using the Canberra Genie 2000 software. For the analyzed radionuclides dose calculations were carried out. The total dose is the sum of the dose contributions of the single radionuclides (GD_i), which are calculated from the activity concentrations (C_i) with the legal valid dose conversion factors ($h(g_i)$) for adults respectively and an annual consumption (KM) of 730 l year^{-1} (IAEA, 1996).

In this survey, mapping of gross alpha and gross beta activity concentrations in drinking water samples (from

water supplies, wells, fountains and from wellsprings) from the territory of Vojvodina province, Serbia, were performed. From totally 820 investigated samples in 73 water samples gross alpha activity exceeded legally established level of 0.1 BqL^{-1} . Additionally, the content of natural radioactive isotopes: ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{238}U in the drinking water samples were determined from a cumulative sample by gamma-spectrometry measurements using the HPGe spectrometer. The total dose due to consumption of these waters was estimated. In 38 investigated samples total dose GD from radionuclides in drinking water is higher than $0.1 \text{ mSv year}^{-1}$ (EC, 1998).

This work was supported by the Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research, Republic of Serbia within the project "Radioactivity in drinking water and cancer incidence in Vojvodina", no. 142-451-2447/2018, the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia within the projects no. OI171002 and III4300.

World Health Organization (WHO), 2011. Guidelines for drinking-water quality, fourth edition. ISBN: 978 92 4 154815 1.

European Commission (EC), 1998. European Drinking Water Directive 98/83/EC of 3 November 1998 on the quality of water intended for human consumption. Official Journal L 330.

International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), 1996. International Basic Safety Standards for Protection against Ionizing Radiation and the Safety Radiation Sources. Safety Report Series, No. 115, Vienna.